

Contents lists available at KMF Publishers

Journal of Policies and Recommendations

journal homepage: www.kmf-publishers.com/jopar/

Research Article

A Critical Analysis of NEP2020 Issues: Challenges, Opportunities and criticism

Amit Anand

Research Scholar, Faculty of Education, L.N.M. University, Darbhanga, India

Corresponding Author Email: amitanand0011@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

New Education Policy, India,
Challenges, Opportunities

ABSTRACT

Education plays a key role in the economic development of any country. Since the early days of Independence, there has always been great focus on improving the literacy rate in India. Every Education policy of India aims at implementing various programmes to promote Primary and Higher Education to a level keeping in view the global scenario. The First Education Policy was Promulgated by Prime Minister Indira Gandhi in 1968, the second by Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi in 1986 and the third by Prime Minister Narendra Modi on 29th July 2020. The New Education Policy replaces the previous National Policy on Education 1986 and forms a comprehensive framework to transform both Elementary and Higher Education in India by 2021. New Education Policy which is also known as NEP focuses on five Pillars :- Affordability, Accessibility, Quality, Equity and Accountability to ensure continuous learning. The NEP 2020 calls for key reforms in both School and Higher Education that prepare the next generation to thrive and compete in the new digital age. NEP 2020 aim to ensure that no child loses any opportunity to learn and excel because of the circumstances of birth or background. There are around 350 million Indians today in School-going and College-going age-groups, the NEP calls for a large scale implementation of a magnitude never before attempted anywhere in the world. This presents substantial execution, challenges both quantitative and qualitative. This article contains the secondary data for collection of information. The necessary secondary data is also collected from various research work, magazines, Journals, websites and other publications etc. This paper also outlines the salient features of NEP and analyses how they affect and reform the existing Education system.

Received 24 March 2022; Received in revised form 28 April 2022; Accepted 8 May 2022

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DOI:

1. Introduction

The National Education Policy 2020 consists of 04 parts and 27 chapters. In the policy, the government of India drafted Various barriers and situations that effect Children Education. The draft initially starts with the introduction part which states about the fundamental requirement of children, how to achieve human potential, development of equality and just in the society, national intergration and cultural preservation. This policy is drafted by the Chairperson of the National Eduaction policy Mr. Krishnaswamy Kasturirangan. It reforms the teacher's recruitment and re-establish a new system to make teachers the most respected and essential member of society. The policy is classified into four parts as part-1-School Education, part-02-Higher Education, Part- 03- Professional Education and all other key ares, Part-04 Strengthening and financing various Education Boards etc.

2. Research Methodology

In this paper an attempt has been made to analyze the New Education policy of India. The data used in it is purely from secondary sources according to the need of this study.

Objectives of the Study

The National Education policy aims to reorient the education system towards meeting the needs of the

21stcentury by achiving the twin objectives of inclusion and excellence. The main Objectives of the programme are:-

- To improve the attractiveness of teaching.
- To Eliminate teacher shortages.
- To Achieve Education for All (EFA) goals.

3. Salient Features of NEP Related to Primary Education :-

The policy provides for reforms at all levels of education from school to higher education. NEP aims to increase the focus on strengthening teacher training, reforming the existing exam system, early childhood care and restructuring the regulatory framework of Education.

The NEP recommended that early childhood care & Education be developed in a two-part Curriculum consisting of:-

- Guidelines for parents & teachers of students up to 3 years of age.
- An educational Frame work for students between the ages of 3-8years.

The NEP talks about the implementation of these recommendation by expanding and improving the quality of the Anganwadi system and Co-locating them with primary School.

The NEP also recommends the 5-3-3-4 pattern explained in the table below:-

Years	Stage	Curriculum
5	Foundational	3Yeats of Pre-primary followed by class 1 and 2
3	Preparatory	Classes 3 to 5
3	Middle	Classes 6 to 8
4	Secondary	Classes 9 to 12

School Exam Reforms

Reforms in the School Exam recommended by the NEP include tracking the progress of the students throughout their school experience:-

- It includes State Census Exam in class 3,5 and 8

- Another important recommendation was the restrcturing of the 10th Board Exam that would mainly focus and test only the skills, core concepts and higher-order thinking and capacities.

Related to Higher Education and research

There are a lot of reforms and new developments which have been introduced by NEP in the higher education sector. Some of the salient features are:-

- Single regulatory body for higher education named as Higher Education commission of India except for legal and medical education.
- There will be multiple entry and exit options for those who wish to leave the course in the middle. Their credits will be transferred through Academic Bank of Credits.
- Tech-based option for adult learning such as apps, online courses/modules, satellite-based TV Channels, online books and Adult Education centers etc. will be developed.
- E-Courses to be available in regional languages starting with 08 major languages- kannada, odia, Bengali, etc.
- World top 100 foreign universities will be facilitated to operate in India.
- UGC and AICTE will be merged.
- All graduation Courses will have major subject and minor like some current management Courses.
- All Universities, government, private, Open, deemed, vocational etc will have the same grading and other rules.
- New Teacher Training board will be setup for all kinds of teachers in country without any authority for states to change it.
- Same level of Accreditation to any college will get autonomous rights and funds.
- 10+2 Board structure is dropped in National Education Policy 2020.
- Students who are doing graduation course will get certificate on the basis of course completion and no student will lose academic year. Basic Certificate after completing one year, Diploma Certificate after completing 2 years and Degree certificate after completing full course.
- All schools examinations will be semester wise twice in a year.
- Credit system for graduations for each year student will get some credits which he / she can utilize if he/she takes break in course and come back again to complete course.

- The National Education policy has also emphasized on setting up of a Gender Inclusion Fund which is aimed at creating an environment of equitable and fair quality education for girls as well as transgender student. As per the NEP Documents, Special Education Zones will be created for disadvantaged regions and groups which will make higher education opportunities more accessible for students.

Research and Development

The Multidisciplinary Education and research universities would form the apex of the Higher Education System. Research in these institutes would be supported by a new national Research Foundation. This will give the necessary impetus to research and development in India. A sum of Rs 50,000 crores was provided for National Research Fund for coming five years in the Union Budget.

Other Reforms

A National Curriculum frame work for Adult Education will be developed to Cover five broad areas:-

- Foundational literacy and numeracy
- Critical life skills
- Vocational skills development
- Basic Education and
- Continuing Education.

Drawbacks of National Policy 2020

India's New Education Policy 2020 has been criticized a lot for the purpose of language. The academic syllabus will be taught in the respective regional languages of the government school students. This is one of the major new education policy drawbacks.

- Planning to spend 6% GDP on Education is a herculean task for Central Government. In the previous year, the country spent less than 3% of its total GDP on Education.
- Allocation quotas is a form of discrimination which is contrary to the right to equality

- 60% of India that is rural needs schools, health, Care and infrastructure in rural areas, not reservation in urban institutions.
- Graduates and Post- graduates will start moving to foreign universities for higher education.
- Opening university every year on an ongoing basis is an undoubtedly massive challenge.
- Developing Anaganwadi centres as a school is dangerous for child education in the present day society.

4. Challenges

The Challenge of New Education Policy is its implementation. Different States have different education systems and hence accepting one uniform education policy would be a bit Challenging. However, we need to understand that through proper participation, we can overcome this challenge and make it successful across the country.

5. Conclusion

With the Introduction of NEP 2020, many changes have been made and one of those is the discontinuation of the M.Phil. course. Even though there are many drawbacks to the new education policy, the merits are more in number. In conclusion we can be hopeful to Academic Study and Research work would bring India on the Educational Map of the world .

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